

POSSIBILITIES OF USING MULTIMEDIA APPLICATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT. In order to improve the effectiveness of the educational process, the need to introduce innovative educational technologies is gaining urgent importance. The use of innovative computer technologies is manifested not only as a method of acquiring knowledge, but also as a means of forming professional competences. A number of modern methods of teaching a foreign language are distinguished and detailed information is given about the tasks of web search technology. The authors come to a conclusion about the feasibility of using web quests as one of the types of innovative technologies in the educational process. , is confirmed by the level of formation of professional skills.

Key words: innovative educational technology, efficiency, formation of professional competences, web search technology, socialization, knowledge activity.

Improving the efficiency of the educational process is an urgent problem of modern society, it is not only management, the complexity of tasks to be solved in production, engineering, science and other fields, but also related to the general trend of the global development of the economic and social situation in Uzbekistan. In accordance with the concept of modernization of education in Uzbekistan, the main goal of professional education in higher education is to prepare a competitive, competent, qualified graduate of the appropriate level and profile, who is able to work effectively at the level of world standards. In the process of training professional personnel, the role of a foreign language, which is becoming a necessary condition for successful professional activity in the context of the integration of the world community and the integration of our country into the world trade and economic system, is gaining urgent importance.

According to researchers, in the field of education innovative technologies create great opportunities for active involvement of students in the educational process. Using innovative technologies, the educational process is used not only as a method of acquiring knowledge, but also as a means of forming professional skills [1]. The use of innovative technologies increases the knowledge activity of

students, allows students to be involved in cooperation in the field of communication, and increases the level of socialization. In the development of new technologies of education, state-shock institutions that regulate the educational process and teachers themselves as an educational task forming the necessary computer-tensions, teachers are involved not directly in imparting knowledge such as achieving a high level of development of students and increasing their motivation for high-quality professional training.

Experience shows that the latest developments in the field of language teaching are interactive are various technical devices and innovative systems of building the educational process. The use of computer technology in the formation of the educational competence approach allows to individualize the educational process, increase the clarity of the presentation of materials, that is, to visualize education, and to conduct a deep and comprehensive analysis of the processes occurring in various systems [2].

In the formation of necessary competences, it is necessary not only to differentiate the educational tasks to be solved, but also to differentiate the educational methodology, methods of using computer technologies in education [2].

These aspects of the implementation of computer technology in the field of education should be far from the last place, which encourages the development of educational systems oriented to a specific field. In the field of education, contemporary information technologies allow to make it more convenient and affordable, to change educational methods and organizational forms in terms of quality [3]. Innovative tools and teaching methods include: web quests, online training , video conferences, open source policy (“distributed” development principle), method of specific situations, virtual reality technology.

Bernie Dodge describes the following tasks for webquests: [4]: retelling; planning and design; compilation; creative assignment; reach consensus; investigative journalism; scientific research. Based on modern requirements for university graduates, the most important tasks can be considered as creative tasks, reaching consensus, journalistic investigations, scientific research. These types of tasks for web quests allow students to fully consider the problems being studied, provide a personal approach to the topic, which helps to enhance the learning process.

The essence of the compilation task is that students need to take information from different sources and bring it to a single format. The final compilation may be published online or presented as a tangible or non-digital

product. For example, it can be a cookbook with recipes collected on the Internet, a booklet, an album containing postcards for tourists, etc. Web quests based on a puzzle task require the synthesis of information from a number of sources and create a puzzle that cannot be solved by simply finding an answer on any Internet page [5]. In journalistic web quests (journalistic tasks), students collect facts and report them, should organize an interview or other journalistic genre. A design web quest (design task) requires students to create a product or plan of action to accomplish a predetermined goal within a specific framework. For example, planning a kitchen that meets the needs of a particular family, or finding a job and planning for college graduates and others.

Creative web quests (creative products task) require students to create any product in a certain format (picture, game, poster, game, song, website, multimedia presentation, etc.). Creative projects are similar in design, but their results are more free and difficult to predict. Web quests for solving controversial problems (consensus building task) involve searching and presenting different, sometimes conflicting opinions on the same problem and trying to bring them to a consensus.

Self-study web quests (self-knowledge tasks) have the goal of helping students better understand themselves, which they can develop through online research. Such projects are rare, but examples still exist, for example, web quests, aimed at exploring Internet resources related to students' future career and work. An analytical web search (an analytical task) examines the interrelationship of things in the real world as part of this theme. Such tasks provide students with the opportunity to carefully study one or more things and find similarities and differences, as well as calculate the hidden meaning of these similarities and differences, understand the relationship of cause and effect, and discuss their significance. [6, 7, 8]. For example, when comparing the cultures of two countries or peoples, it is not necessary to identify their similarities and differences, but to think and speculate about what they mean about their causes and effects.

Assessment web quests (judgment tasks) present students with a range of topics and are required to evaluate or classify them or choose a solution from a large list. Often, but not necessarily, students are encouraged to participate in such assignments, such as a mock trial of judges. Scientific web quests (scientific tasks) serve to introduce and acquaint students with scientific research in various fields. The topic of web quests can be the most diverse, problem assignments can vary in complexity.

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